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Research Article

**STUDY TO DETERMINE THE EFFECT OF
POSTPONEMENT IN ACUTE APPENDICITIS SURGERY**Dr. Nasrullah Zadran¹, Dr Nasir Iqbal², Dr Amir Farooq Khan³^{1,3} Khyber Medical College Peshawar² Khyber Medical University Institute of Medical Sciences Kohat**Article Received:** June 2020**Accepted:** July 2020**Published:** August 2020**Abstract:****Aim:** To determine the frequency and risk factors of perforation in acute appendicitis.**Study design:** A retrospective study.**Place and Duration:** In the Surgical department of Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar for one-year duration from April 2019 to April 2020.**Material and methods:** A total of 150 patients were included in the study. Data on age, gender, patient intervals, hospital stay, results of surgery, and histopathological report were recorded in a proforma format. Preoperatively appendix was divided into 5 types as normal, cattedral, phlegmonous, gangrenous, and perforated which were confirmed by histopathology report**Results:** Of 150 patients there were 87 (58%) men and 63 (42%) women. The mean age of the patients was 23.94 years, ranging from 10 to 60 years. The negative appendectomy and perforation rates were 6.7% and 10%, respectively. Mean patient interval in the perforated group was 71.33 hours while mean hospital interval was 6.61 hours in the perforated group.**Conclusion:** Age and inter-patient interval are important factors of perforation in acute appendicitis.**Key words:** acute appendicitis, perforated appendix, patient interval, hospital interval.**Corresponding author:****Dr. Nasrullah Zadran,**

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INTRODUCTION:

Appendicitis is the most common cause of abdominal surgery in all age groups^{1, 2}. Acute appendicitis develops in nearly 10% of the general population with a maximum incidence in the second and third decades of life¹⁻². Late diagnosis and surgical intervention are considered an important cause of morbidity in acute appendicitis. Acute appendicitis can progress to gangrene and perforation if not easily diagnosed and treated³⁻⁴. Various factors are responsible for perforation in acute appendicitis in different age groups, which may be explained by the difference in immunity status and the etiology of appendicitis. Perforation in acute appendicitis is responsible for increased morbidity (6% to 17%), mortality, prolonged hospital stays, and the patient's financial burden⁵⁻⁶. Therefore, many surgeons recommend early appendicitis at the expense of diagnostic accuracy to prevent perforation in acute appendicitis. However, recent reports of successful conservative treatment of acute appendicitis in children with intravenous antibiotics and fluids negate the popular concept of early appendectomy⁷⁻⁸. Early appendectomy excludes perforation, but it certainly increases morbidity, hospital stay, and patient treatment costs. Most of the patients in our unit belong to the lower socio-economic group⁹⁻¹⁰. This study will help determine whether a time factor plays a role in disease progression in acute appendicitis, and in light of the results of this study, appropriate measures will be taken to reduce the morbidity, mortality and treatment costs of patients with acute appendicitis.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

A retrospective analysis, with approval from the Medical Ethics Committee, was conducted on 150 consecutive patients who had emergency appendectomy due to acute appendicitis at the Surgical department of Lady Reading Hospital Peshawar for one-year duration from April 2019 to April 2020. Patient data on age, gender, time between onset of symptoms and admission to hospital, time between admission to hospital and removal of appendix, results of surgery, and histopathological report were taken from the patients' hospital records and recorded on a

proforma form. Patients with no documented onset of symptoms or abnormal history were excluded from the study. The time between onset of symptoms and admission to hospital was taken as the interval between patients and expressed in hours. Similarly, the time between admission to hospital and removal of the appendix was denoted as the hospitalization interval, which was also expressed in hours. During the perioperative period, the appendix has been classified into five types, normal appendicitis (negative appendectomy), catarrhal appendicitis, gangrenous appendicitis, appendicitis, and perforated appendicitis. Perioperative criteria for the various degrees of inflammation were hyperemia, edema, dilated blood vessels, and appendicitis with or without perforation. The pre- and perioperative diagnosis of acute appendicitis and the degree of inflammation were confirmed by a pathologist's histopathological report. Data analysis was performed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 10). Frequency and percentages were calculated for categorical data such as gender, operating outcome, and continuous data such as age, inter-patient interval, and hospital interval are presented as mean \pm SD. The Chi-square test was used to compare the frequencies of categorical variables, and the t test was used to compare the means for continuous variables. A p value less than 0.05 ($p < 0.05$) was considered significant.

RESULTS:

The study involved a total of 150 patients who underwent appendectomy due to acute appendicitis, justifying the selection criteria. There were 58% ($n = 87$) men and 42% ($n = 63$) women, and the ratio of men to women was 1.3: 1. The mean age of the patients was 23 ± 9.4 years, ranging from 10 to 60 years, as shown in figure 1. The mean age of men was 21.89 ± 8.71 years compared with 24.31 ± 10.17 years for women. Accurate histopathology showed that the diagnosis of acute appendicitis was made in 93.3% ($n = 140$) of patients, with 6.7% ($n = 10$) being a negative appendectomy index. The sex indexes and distribution of different degrees of inflammation according to the histopathological report are presented in Table 1.

Table 1: Gender distribution in operative findings

	Operative Findings					Total
	C	P	G	Pr	N	
Gender	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Male	66 (44)	4 (2.6)	1 (0.6)	13 (8.6)	3 (2)	87 (58)
Female	53 (35)	1 (0.6)	0 (0)	2 (1.3)	7 (4.6)	63 (42)
Total	119 (79)	5 (3.2)	1 (0.6)	15 (10)	10 (6.6)	150 (100)

C=Cattahral appendicitis; G=Gangrenous appendicitis; N=Negative appendectomy; P=Phlegmonous appendicitis; Pr=Perforated appendicitis

According to Table 1, the male appendix was cattahral in 44%, pyoderma in 2.6%, gangrene in 0.6%, perforated in 8.6% and normal at 2%. The respective figures for women were 35%, 0.6%, 0%, 1.3%, and 4.6%, respectively. Negative appendectomy was common in women 70% (n = 7) compared with men 30% (n = 3). The final diagnosis in patients with negative appendectomy was Meckel's diverticulitis (n = 2), ureteral colic (n = 3), ruptured ovarian cyst (n = 4), and ectopic pregnancy (n = 1). As shown in Table 1, the perforation rate was 10% (n = 15). The mean age of the patients with perforated appendicitis was 30.20 ± 15.63 years compared with 22.09 ± 8.46 years in the non-perforated appendicitis group (p-value = 0.002).

Table 2: Age and Gender stratification in perforated appendicitis

Age group	Perforated appendicitis (%)		Total (n)
	Male (n)	Female (n)	
11-20 years	4 (80%)	1 (20%)	5 (33.33%)
21-30 years	5 (100%)	0 (0%)	5 (33.33%)
31-40 years	1 (100%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.66%)
41-50 years	2 (66.66%)	1 (33.33%)	3 (20%)
Above 50 years	1 (100%)	0 (0%)	1 (6.66%)

The frequency of perforation in men and women in different age groups is presented in Table 2. Perforation was frequent in men 86.66% (n = 13) than in women 13.33% (n = 2), significant (p-value = 0.001), with a male ratio of women to 6.5: 1.

Table 3: Patient interval in different grades of inflammation of appendicitis

Duration of time before admission	Cattahral	Phlegmonous	Gangrenous	Perforated	Total
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Less than 24 hrs	103 (94.4)	3 (2.7)		3 (2.75)	109 (77.8)
24-48 hrs	7 (50)	2 (14.2)	1 (7.14)	4 (28.5)	14 (10)
48-72 hrs	4 (50)			4 (50)	8 (5.7)
More than 72 hrs	5 (55.5)			4 (44.4)	9 (6.4)
Total patients	119 (100)	5 (100)	1 (100)	15 (100)	140 (100)

Negative appendectomy excluded.

The mean interval between patients in the perforated group was significantly longer (71.33 ± 44.69 hours) than the interval in the group without perforation, 26.67 ± 24.60 hours, (P-value <0.001). Intervals between patients with different degrees of appendicitis are stratified in Table 3 which shows that 8 patients (53.3%) waited more than 48 hours before arriving at the hospital. The mean hospitalization period was 6.61 ± 2.46 hours in patients without perforation versus 13.60 ± 29.51 hours in patients with perforation in appendicitis (p-value > 0.05).

Table 4: Hospital interval in different grades of inflammation

Duration b/w admission and appendectomy	Cattahral	Phlegmonous	Gangrenous	Perforated	Total
	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)	n (%)
Less than 6 hrs	37 (80.4)	1 (2.1)		8 (17.3)	46 (32.8)
6-12 hrs	79 (88.7)	4 (4.4)	1 (4.4)	5 (5.6)	89 (63.5)
12-24 hrs	3 (75)			1 (25)	4 (2.8)
More than 24 hrs				1 (100)	1 (0.7)
Total	119 (100)	5 (100)	1 (100)	15 (100)	140 (100)

Negative appendectomy excluded.

As shown in Table 4, showing the hospitalization period, over 96% of patients were operated on within 12 hours of admission.

DISCUSSION:

There has been little change in the epidemiology of acute appendicitis in the last 25 years, with the

disease becoming almost as prevalent in men and women, with a recent male-to-female ratio of 1.2: 1. This study also shows that no There was a

significant difference in the incidence of appendicitis in both sexes with a male to female ratio of 1.3: 1. Another study produced nearly comparable results (male to female ratio 0.94: 1)¹¹. A study by Rawalpindi General Hospital found a higher male to female ratio of 1.94: 1 in 150 patients with acute appendicitis. In a retrospective review of 140 post-appendicitis patients, 52 women developed acute appendicitis with a male-to-female ratio of 1.7: 14. A higher male-to-female ratio of appendicitis occurs in adolescents, and the results of this study are fairly consistent with generally accepted data¹². The mean age of the patients with acute appendicitis in this study was 23 years. This observation is in line with the results of other national studies. In studies from Hong Kong and Sweden, the average age of appendicitis patients is 33 and 31 years old, which is quite high compared to our results. Acute appendicitis is rare in infants, with the highest incidence in the second and third decades of life, as confirmed by the results of this study. Although treating appendicitis is simple and straightforward, the main difficulty is diagnosing it. The clinical picture of acute appendicitis may mimic other inflammations of the abdomen and thorax, and the classic symptoms of migrating pain in the right lower quadrant, fever, anorexia, nausea and vomiting may only be seen in 50 to 60% of patients, making it difficult to diagnose¹³. In our study, a total of ten (6.7%) patients were misdiagnosed, which was confirmed by histopathological examination. According to the results of this study, women of childbearing age (due to pelvic gynecological diseases) are most often misdiagnosed in older age and children (atypical picture). Ali N *et al*. Reported a very high percentage of 24% negative appendages compared to our results. The Hyderabad study, unlike our study, showed a lower rate of 3.78%, while contrary to our results, the Iran and Sweden studies showed almost double the number of negative appendectomies, 14% and 13.6% respectively. In patients with atypical clinical features, diagnostic laparoscopy should be the first-line option instead of CT, U / S or follow-up due to the excellent diagnostic results of laparoscopy and the low efficiency of U / S and CT in ambiguous cases. The obstruction of the lumen of the appendix can be caused by external or internal factors causing increased mucus production and stagnation with increased wall tension above the perfusion pressure, leading to necrosis and perforation¹⁴. Delay in diagnosis and treatment is an important factor leading to perforation as it explains the time-dependent mechanism well above. The main finding in this study was that patients with perforated appendicitis had a significant interval before hospitalization (2.67 times longer) as opposed to patients with non-perforated appendicitis. This finding has been previously

reported in several other studies which show that the delay before admission is strongly associated with the risk of perforation in acute appendicitis. Fahim F *et al*. Found that patient intervals did not significantly affect the outcomes of acute appendicitis, contrary to our findings. Intervals between hospitalizations have little effect on the perforation of acute appendages, and similar results were found in this study. Our finding was supported by previous data, although others believe that prolonged hospitalization due to repeated observations is responsible for the perforation. In this study, perforation was more common in men than in women, which is consistent with previous reports. The difference in immune response between males and females may be responsible for this difference in the rate of perforation. The mean age of the patients with perforated appendicitis was 30.20 years, with 26.66% of patients > 40 years of age and 33.33% of patients < 20 years of age. One of the shortcomings of this study was that children under the age of 10 were not included as they were rarely operated on in our unit¹⁵. This study does not show an increased rate of perforation at extreme age and is well distributed among different age groups. In previous studies, perforation rates of 37% and 48% were reported in patients over 50 years of age. There are also articles suggesting that younger children have an increased rate of perforation, which may be attributed to the unusual symptom of appendicitis in this age group.

CONCLUSION:

This study concluded that the age of the patients, male gender and delayed admission to hospital are important factors leading to perforation in acute appendicitis. These results confirm that there is a strong need to educate patients in the search for early health care in abdominal pain situations, as well as in identifying the factors that delay patients' admission to hospital.

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